

Inside your body (Introceptive)

You will be asked to rate how much you experience everyday concepts using perceptual senses. There are no right or wrong answers so please use your own judgement. The rating scale runs from 0 (not experienced at all with that sense) to 5 (experienced greatly with that sense). Please answer only with the number.

To what extent do you experience by sensations inside your body word "X"

Taste (Gustatory)

You will be asked to rate how much you experience everyday concepts using perceptual senses. There are no right or wrong answers so please use your own judgement. The rating scale runs from 0 (not experienced at all with that sense) to 5 (experienced greatly with that sense). Please answer only with the number.

To what extent do you experience by tasting word "X"

Smell (Olfactory)

You will be asked to rate how much you experience everyday concepts using perceptual senses. There are no right or wrong answers so please use your own judgement. The rating scale runs from 0 (not experienced at all with that sense) to 5 (experienced greatly with that sense). Please answer only with the number.

To what extent do you experience by smelling word "X"

Touch (Haptic)

You will be asked to rate how much you experience everyday concepts using perceptual senses. There are no right or wrong answers so please use your own judgement. The rating scale runs from 0 (not experienced at all with that sense) to 5 (experienced greatly with that sense). Please answer only with the number.

To what extent do you experience by feeling through touch "X"

Hear (Auditory)

You will be asked to rate how much you experience everyday concepts using perceptual senses. There are no right or wrong answers so please use your own judgement. The rating scale runs from 0 (not experienced at all with that sense) to 5 (experienced greatly with that sense). Please answer only with the number.

To what extent do you experience by hearing "X"

Sight (Visual)

You will be asked to rate how much you experience everyday concepts using perceptual senses. There are no right or wrong answers so please use your own judgement. The rating scale runs from 0 (not experienced at all with that sense) to 5 (experienced greatly with that sense). Please answer only with the number.

To what extent do you experience by feeling through seeing "X"